

GOALS AND OBJECTIVES OF THE INTRODUCTION OF ELECTRONIC LEARNING IN TEACHING SUBJECTS

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Abstract. The article is devoted to the goals and objectives of the introduction of electronic learning in teaching subjects. Electronic learning is defined as a set of forms, methods and means of the educational process based on information technologies. The article lists a number of problems in the introduction of electronic learning (the use of modern IT, the creation of electronic educational literature, the clarification of teacher activities) and the lack of readiness of pedagogical teams.

Keywords: electronic education (E-learning), information technologies, informatization of education, educational process, individualization, material and technical base, self-control, electronic educational literature

The introduction of electronic education into the education system directly depends, first of all, on the intellectual potential of teachers, as well as on the informatization of the educational sphere. The acquisition of deep knowledge by students depends on the level of mastering the basics of science and how well their skills in information technologies are formed.

Electronic education is a set of forms, methods, techniques and means of implementing the educational process based on information technology, which allows achieving educational goals.

The main goals of the sequential and phased introduction of electronic education into the education system are:

- development of a mechanism for introducing electronic education into the education system;
- creation of an information system of the educational process in secondary schools;

The implementation of electronic educational technologies in the teaching of subjects depends primarily on the state of the material and technical base of educational institutions, in this sense, the main tasks in improving education based on information and communication technologies are as follows:

- creation of the necessary material and technical base for the implementation of electronic education in the educational process;
- creation and application of educational technologies for e-learning for the educational process;
- formation of students' knowledge and skills in the field of modern electronic education technologies;
- to increase the effectiveness of the educational and training process by introducing electronic education.

Today, there are the following problems in introducing e-learning into the educational system:

- use of modern information technologies in teaching all subjects;
- creation of electronic educational literature on subjects, their use in the educational system, in particular, in distance education;
- it is necessary to clarify the activity of the teacher in electronic education.

The stages of organizing an electronic educational environment in a secondary school begin with the creation of a psychological information environment. Based on technological and scientific results, created software products, the need for the use of modern tools and methods is formed. In this regard, it is necessary to organize a system of independent and computer training of teachers on the basis of individual and advisory classes in each secondary school.

The use of computer tools in an electronic educational environment can be divided into two areas: mastering all methods of using a computer as a means of educational activity and using a computer as an object of study. The improvement of information tools and computer software, the expansion of its didactic capabilities reveal its new properties as a means of teaching.

The described general approach to understanding the essence of electronic education allows us to draw a conclusion about its sufficient complexity.

Today, there are a number of problems in the implementation of electronic education:

- insufficient readiness of pedagogical teams to implement electronic education;
- lack of awareness of the possibilities of electronic education among subject teachers, lack of potential for their application;
- lack of specialists in the implementation of electronic education.

Electronic education leads to such unexpected results in pedagogical practice that it opens up new facets of the educational process.

The following methodological goals are achieved through the implementation of electronic education:

- individualization and differentiation of the learning process;
- monitoring of learning activities with electronic feedback;
- self-control;
- organization of exercises and independent training in the process of mastering educational material;
- saving learning time;
- visualization of educational information on a computer;
- modeling of phenomena and processes being studied;
- creation and use of an information database;
- increasing interest in learning;
- equipping students with strategies for mastering educational material;
- development of thinking;
- formation of optimal decision-making skills of the student;
- formation of information culture in the student, etc. can be included.

Electronic education expands the possibilities of obtaining information, in addition, it allows multiple access to the information source, using several information channels at the same time. Through the channels, the student gains experience in using a combination of auditory, visual, audiovisual and other methods of receiving information. The ability to simultaneously use different channels of receiving information increases the student's

attention to the material being presented, accelerates and improves the quality of the learning process, increases his mobilization in receiving information presented in various forms.

Thus, the use of electronic education leads to a change in organizational forms and methods of teaching, as well as the formation of new methods in it.

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